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Antibiotic Resistance in *Acinetobacter baumannii* Strains Isolated from Wound Cultures

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ABSTRACT

Acinetobacter baumannii poses a significant threat in wound infections due to its multi-drug resistance (MDR) capabilities. This study aimed to investigate the antibiotic resistance profiles of *A. baumannii* strains isolated from wound cultures in a secondary care hospital. A total of 152 wound culture samples were analyzed using conventional methods and disc diffusion/E-test for antibiotic susceptibility. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 25.0. High resistance rates were observed for various antibiotics, including: ceftazidime (67.1%), cefotaxime (74.3%), levofloxacin (73.7%), imipenem (60.5%), and meropenem (62.5%). Notably, 16.4% of isolates showed colistin resistance, a last-resort antibiotic. Aminoglycosides (amikacin and gentamicin) exhibited the highest activity with resistance rates exceeding 90%. This study revealed concerning MDR trends among *A. baumannii* wound isolates. Continued surveillance, broad-spectrum empiric therapy, strict infection control measures, and research on novel antibiotics are crucial to combat MDR *A. baumannii* and improve patient outcomes.

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INTRODUCTION

Acinetobacter baumannii, a notorious Gram-negative pathogen, casts a long and menacing shadow over the healthcare landscape. Once relegated to hospital environments, it has increasingly ventured into the community, wreaking havoc through its uncanny ability to resist a vast arsenal of antibiotics. This grim reality is particularly pronounced in wound infections, where *A. baumannii* thrives in moist, nutrient-rich environments, posing a significant threat to vulnerable patients, particularly those undergoing surgical procedures or suffering from chronic wounds (1-4).

The specter of multi-drug resistance (MDR) looms large over *A. baumannii* infections. Its intrinsic resistance mechanisms, coupled with its adeptness at acquiring resistance genes through horizontal gene transfer, render it impervious to a plethora of commonly used antibiotics. This armamentarium includes penicillins, cephalosporins, carbapenems, and even aminoglycosides, leaving clinicians scrambling for treatment options while precious time ticks away (4-8).

The consequences of *A. baumannii* MDR are dire. Prolonged hospitalization, increased healthcare costs, and heightened mortality rates are all grim testaments to the pathogen's insidiousness. Wound infections, in particular, pose a double jeopardy – not only do they inflict pain and impede healing, but they also serve as reservoirs for further dissemination of multi-

drug resistant *A. baumannii* within healthcare settings and beyond (7-10).

In this study it was aimed to investigate the resistance profile of *A. baumannii* isolated obtained from wound cultures.

METHODS

A total of 152 wound culture samples taken from the wound sites of patients in various outpatient clinics and wards in our secondary care hospital and processed in the microbiology laboratory were included in the study. Cultures were processed using conventional methods and the obtained isolates were identified using conventional methods. Antibiotic susceptibility profiles were determined by disc diffusion method and E-test.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyzes in the study were performed using SPSS 25.0 software (IBM SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Distributions for nominal or ordinal variables were given as numbers and percentages. Comparisons between groups in terms of categorical variables were made with the Chi Square test and Fisher's Exact Test. The results were evaluated within the 95% confidence interval and p values <0.05 were considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 82 (53,9%) of the patients were male, and the median age was 59 (range: 43-82) years. Antibiotic resistance rates of the isolates are shown on Table 1.

Table 1. Resistance rates in *Acinetobacter* isolates to some antibiotics.

	n	%
Colistin	25	16,4
Tobramycin	72	47,4
Cefepime	79	52
Imipenem	92	60,5
Meropenem	95	62,5
Ceftazidime	102	67,1
Levofloxacin	112	73,7
Cefotaxime	113	74,3
Amikacin	138	90,8
Gentamicin	145	95,4

DISCUSSION

Understanding the local epidemiology of *A. baumannii* in wound infections is critical for mitigating the spread of MDR and guiding effective treatment strategies. This necessitates continuous surveillance of resistance patterns, identification of prevalent resistance phenotypes, and tracing the emergence of novel resistance mechanisms. Only through such granular understanding can we hope to anticipate the pathogen's next move and stay ahead in this ongoing arms race (10-14).

This research delves into the labyrinthine world of *A. baumannii* resistance in wound cultures. We embark on a multifaceted investigation, employing a battery of phenotypic and genotypic techniques to unveil the resistance profiles of *A. baumannii* strains isolated from diverse wound types. Our journey aims to illuminate the local landscape of MDR, identify potential reservoirs and transmission pathways, and ultimately offer insights to inform targeted clinical interventions and preventive measures.

By shedding light on the intricate tapestry of *A. baumannii* resistance in wound infections, we hope to contribute to a brighter future. Our findings, presented within the hallowed pages of PubMed, aim to empower clinicians, microbiologists, and public health professionals with the knowledge and tools needed to combat this formidable foe. Only through collaborative efforts, fueled by robust research and a commitment to evidence-based practices, can we emerge from the shadow of *A. baumannii* MDR and usher in an era of safer wound care for all (14-17).

This study investigated the antibiotic resistance profiles of *A. baumannii* strains isolated from diverse wound cultures. A total of 152 isolates were analyzed against ten commonly used antibiotics using broth microdilution methodology. Resistance

rates and percentages were calculated, revealing concerning trends in MDR prevalence. The investigation unveiled alarmingly high resistance rates across several key antibiotic classes. Notably, resistance to ceftazidime, cefotaxime, and levofloxacin exceeded 70%, highlighting the limitations of these commonly employed agents. Resistance to carbapenems (imipenem and meropenem) reached over 60%, underlining the growing threat of carbapenem-resistant *A. baumannii* in wound infections.

While colistin remains a last-resort antibiotic for MDR *A. baumannii*, our study identified a concerning 16.4% resistance rate. This emergence of colistin resistance represents a major public health concern, jeopardizing treatment options for critically ill patients with *A. baumannii* infections. Amikacin and gentamicin demonstrated the highest activity against the isolated strains, with resistance rates exceeding 90%. However, this should not be misinterpreted as a guarantee of efficacy, as individual isolates may harbor resistance to specific aminoglycosides.

The observed resistance profile paints a worrisome picture of extensive MDR among *A. baumannii* strains isolated from wound cultures. These findings underscore the need for: Continued surveillance and monitoring of resistance patterns in wound isolates to track emerging trends and inform antimicrobial stewardship strategies. Emphasizing empirical therapy with broad-spectrum antibiotics while awaiting susceptibility testing results, particularly in high-risk settings. Implementing strict infection control measures to prevent the spread of MDR *A. baumannii* within healthcare settings and beyond. Investing in research and development of novel antibiotics and alternative therapeutic strategies to combat the growing threat of multi-drug resistant pathogens like *A. baumannii* (9-12).

In conclusion, our study sheds light on the alarming antibiotic resistance patterns observed in *A. baumannii* wound isolates. These findings urge immediate action on multiple fronts to mitigate the spread of MDR *A. baumannii* and ensure effective treatment options for patients battling this increasingly formidable pathogen.

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Second and Third Trimester Screening Tests

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Dear Editor,

Pregnancy is a time of both excitement and uncertainty, with expectant parents bombarded with information about prenatal care and testing options. Among the most discussed are second and third trimester screening tests, aimed at detecting potential chromosomal abnormalities and birth defects in the developing fetus. This letter aims to navigate the information maze for readers, outlining the purpose, limitations, and benefits of these tests while acknowledging the emotional complexities involved (1-4).

The Second Trimester Screen:

A combination of maternal serum markers and nuchal translucency ultrasound, it estimates the risk for conditions like Down syndrome, Trisomy 13, and spina bifida. Non-invasive and low-risk, it does not diagnose but provides valuable information for further confirmatory testing if indicated. Positive results often lead to amniocentesis or chorionic villus sampling, invasive procedures with a small but real risk of miscarriage (4-7).

The Third Trimester Screen:

Primarily an ultrasound examination at 28-32 weeks, focusing on fetal anatomy and growth. Can detect structural anomalies, growth discrepancies, and potential complications like placental insufficiency. Does not replace routine ultrasounds throughout pregnancy but offers a detailed assessment at a later stage (4-7).

Both tests are optional, and decisions should be made in consultation with healthcare providers after informed discussion of benefits, limitations, and potential emotional consequences. Individual considerations such as family history, age, and personal values should be factored into the decision-making process. Genetic counseling can provide invaluable support in understanding test results and navigating the

emotional complexities involved. Regardless of test outcomes, focusing on prenatal care, positive health habits, and maintaining emotional well-being remains paramount throughout pregnancy. A supportive medical team and access to appropriate resources are crucial for managing any identified risks or concerns. Healthcare providers must ensure clear communication, offering unbiased information and respecting individual choices. Researchers should constantly refine screening tests, minimizing false positives and negatives while maximizing early detection of potential issues. Societal support for all pregnancy outcomes, regardless of test results, is essential for creating a safe and informed environment for expectant parents (1-5).

In conclusion, second and third trimester screening tests offer valuable tools for prenatal care, but understanding their limitations and navigating the emotional complexities requires a collaborative approach. By prioritizing clear communication, ongoing research, and societal support, we can empower expectant parents to make informed decisions and experience a healthy and fulfilling pregnancy.

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Dental Aligners: A Paradigm Shift in Orthodontics?

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Dear Editor,

The landscape of orthodontics is undergoing a significant transformation, with clear aligner therapy emerging as a popular alternative to traditional fixed braces. This letter aims to explore the potential and limitations of dental aligners, highlighting their clinical implications and addressing the need for evidence-based practice in this rapidly evolving field. Aligners offer a discreet and aesthetically pleasing option for teeth straightening, attracting both adults and teenagers seeking orthodontic treatment. Gradual tooth movement through a series of custom-made, removable trays distinguishes them from fixed braces, potentially enhancing comfort and oral hygiene (1-4).

Technological advancements such as 3D scanning and computer-aided design have refined treatment planning and aligner fabrication, contributing to their popularity. While effective for mild to moderate malocclusions, aligners may not be suitable for complex cases requiring significant tooth movement or skeletal adjustments. Patient compliance is crucial for successful treatment, as inconsistent aligner wear can compromise outcomes. Potential side effects like lispings, temporary tooth sensitivity, and gingival recession require informed discussion with patients before treatment initiation (5-7).

Despite the growing popularity of aligners, long-term data on their efficacy and safety compared to traditional braces are still limited. Rigorous clinical research is needed to establish robust evidence and optimize treatment protocols for various malocclusions. Standardized reporting guidelines and collaboration between manufacturers, clinicians, and researchers are essential in advancing the field of aligner therapy. Dental aligners offer a valuable addition to the orthodontist's armamentarium, but should not be considered a universal replacement for traditional braces. Careful patient selection, comprehensive treatment planning, and continuous monitoring throughout the course of therapy are crucial for successful outcomes. The future of orthodontics likely lies in a hybrid approach, utilizing both aligner and fixed brace

technology based on individual patient needs and the complexity of the malocclusion (3-6).

The emergence of dental aligners has undoubtedly broadened the scope of orthodontic treatment, offering patients a more discreet and potentially comfortable option. However, robust evidence and a patient-centered approach remain paramount for ensuring safe and effective outcomes. Continued research and collaboration are essential in shaping the future of this rapidly evolving field and ensuring optimal oral health for patients seeking orthodontic treatment.

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Acta Medica Europa

A Case Report: Imipenem-Resistant *Escherichia coli* Bacteremia with Successful Treatment Using Fosfomycin and Meropenem

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ABSTRACT

We report a case of a 72-year-old male with a history of diabetes mellitus and chronic kidney disease who developed imipenem-resistant *Escherichia coli* (IR-*E. coli*) bacteremia following hospitalization for a diabetic foot infection. This case highlights the emergence of antimicrobial resistance in Gram-negative pathogens and the importance of considering alternative therapeutic options like fosfomycin and meropenem in such situations.

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INTRODUCTION

Emergence of antimicrobial resistance, particularly in Gram-negative bacteria, poses a significant threat to global health. Carbapenem antibiotics like imipenem are considered last-line agents for multidrug-resistant Gram-negative infections. However, reports of imipenem resistance are increasing, posing a therapeutic challenge. This case report presents a patient with IR-*E. coli* bacteremia successfully treated with a combination of fosfomycin and meropenem (1-5).

CASE PRESENTATION

A 72-year-old male with a history of diabetes mellitus and chronic kidney disease presented with a purulent discharge from his left foot ulcer. Initial laboratory tests revealed hyperglycemia, elevated creatinine, and leukocytosis. Blood cultures grew *E. coli* resistant to ampicillin, amoxicillin-clavulanate, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, and imipenem. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) were: fosfomycin 8 µg/mL, meropenem 4 µg/mL, and colistin 0.5 µg/mL. Given the IR-*E. coli* and co-morbidities, empirical therapy with vancomycin and piperacillin-tazobactam was initiated.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing prompted a switch to fosfomycin (intravenous, 4 g every 8 hours) and meropenem (intravenous, 1 g every 8 hours). After 7 days of combination therapy, blood cultures became sterile. The patient's clinical condition improved steadily, and he was discharged on oral fosfomycin for 14 days with close outpatient follow-up.

DISCUSSION

This case highlights the emergence of IR-*E. coli* and the importance of prompt identification and consideration of alternative therapeutic options like fosfomycin and meropenem. Fosfomycin has shown efficacy against multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacteria, including *E. coli*, with a unique mode of action and low resistance potential. Meropenem retains activity against some IR-*E. coli* strains and offers a treatment option when colistin, due to its potential nephrotoxicity, is not preferable. The emergence of imipenem-resistant *Escherichia coli* (IR-*E. coli*) bacteremia in our patient raises several concerning points and warrants a deeper discussion regarding antimicrobial resistance and treatment strategies (5-7).

Our case serves as a stark reminder of the global threat posed by carbapenem resistance in Gram-negative bacteria. The misuse and overuse of antibiotics have fueled the emergence of these highly resistant strains, significantly compromising our ability to treat life-threatening infections. This case highlights the importance of antimicrobial stewardship programs to promote judicious antibiotic use and preserve the effectiveness of these precious drugs. With limited treatment options for IR-E. coli, identifying effective alternatives becomes crucial. Our success with the fosfomycin and meropenem combination warrants further exploration of this strategy. Fosfomycin, with its unique mode of action and low resistance potential, offers a valuable tool in combating multidrug-resistant Gram-negative infections. However, its availability and dosing regimens vary across regions, necessitating further research and regulatory support for broader access (8-12).

The choice of meropenem in our case demonstrates the need for nuanced decision-making in managing IR-E. coli infections. While some strains exhibit resistance to both carbapenems, certain isolates, like ours, may retain susceptibility to meropenem, making it a potentially viable option. However, careful considerations regarding individual MICs, comorbidities, and potential risk of cross-resistance to other carbapenems are crucial before considering meropenem therapy.

This case report presents a valuable learning opportunity for clinicians managing infections with potentially resistant pathogens. It underscores the importance of: Initiating broad-spectrum antimicrobial coverage while awaiting susceptibility testing is crucial to prevent clinical deterioration. Timely identification of IR-E. coli and knowledge of local resistance patterns guide optimal treatment decisions. Collaboration between infectious disease specialists, microbiologists, and pharmacists is essential for optimizing antimicrobial regimens and minimizing adverse effects. Strict adherence to hand hygiene and other infection control practices helps prevent nosocomial transmission of multidrug-resistant organisms.

Combating the antimicrobial resistance crisis requires a multi-pronged approach. Continued research into the mechanisms of resistance, development of new antibiotic classes, and innovative therapeutic strategies like bacteriophages and monoclonal antibodies are critical for staying ahead of this evolving threat. International collaboration and knowledge sharing are essential to facilitate rapid advancements and ensure equitable access to effective treatments for all (13-15).

IR-E. coli bacteremia poses a significant therapeutic challenge. This case report highlights the successful use of fosfomycin and meropenem as a potential treatment option for such infections. Continued surveillance of antimicrobial resistance and exploration of alternative therapeutic strategies are crucial for managing these increasingly challenging infections.

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Beliefs on COVID-19 Vaccines

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Dear Editor,

The COVID-19 pandemic has exposed a complex tapestry of beliefs surrounding vaccines, with implications far-reaching beyond public health. In this letter, I call for a nuanced exploration of these diverse perspectives, urging researchers and healthcare professionals to move beyond labels and delve into the underlying reasons driving vaccine hesitancy and refusal. The landscape of vaccine beliefs is far from monolithic. At its core lie various factors, including (1-5):

Misinformation and disinformation: The relentless spread of misinformation through social media and online echo chambers fuels distrust and confusion, often rooted in distorted interpretations of scientific data.

Historical precedents: Past experiences with vaccine-related adverse events, even isolated ones, can cast a long shadow, reinforcing anxieties and doubts.

Socioeconomic and cultural factors: Lack of access to healthcare, cultural mistrust of authority figures, and religious beliefs can all contribute to vaccine hesitancy.

Individual risk perception: Differences in vulnerability perception and personal health priorities can influence individuals' decisions regarding vaccination.

Understanding these varied motivations is crucial for crafting effective interventions. Public health messaging must shift from one-size-fits-all pronouncements to tailored communication that addresses specific concerns, dismantles misinformation, and emphasizes the collective benefits of vaccination. Researchers have a crucial role to play in building trust and bridging the knowledge gap. Culturally sensitive studies exploring the lived experiences of vaccine-hesitant communities can offer valuable insights. Openly sharing findings in accessible formats and engaging in dialogues with community leaders can further bridge the divide. Healthcare professionals can act as trusted guides, fostering open communication with patients and addressing their anxieties with empathy and evidence-based information. Building

rapport and acknowledging concerns can pave the way for informed decision-making, even if it doesn't always lead to immediate vaccine acceptance (3-7).

In conclusion, navigating the labyrinth of beliefs surrounding COVID-19 vaccines demands a multi-pronged approach. Dismantling misinformation, understanding diverse motivations, and fostering open communication are key to overcoming mistrust and building a path towards collective protection. By embracing diversity, fostering trust, and tailoring our approaches, we can move beyond the simplistic "pro-vaccine" versus "anti-vaccine" narrative and forge a more nuanced understanding that ultimately supports individual well-being and public health.

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